

Together We Depict People's Reading and Browsing Behavior on Public Transit: A Pedagogical Approach Addressing Contextual Inquiry

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ABSTRACT

This poster presents data collected through an information behavior course from 2014 to 2023 and introduces how the instructor guided the students through the contextual inquiry process. With 1307 cases observed by about 435 students over the last ten years, we depict people's reading and browsing behavior on public transit in a metropolitan area consisting of two large cities and one surrounding city that is densely populated with more than 7 million people. With a contextual inquiry approach, each student was asked to observe three cases and conduct the analysis through a guided in-class discussion with their peers. Preliminary thoughts were generated afterward and debriefed in class. The instructor consolidated students' findings based on their observation notes and integrated the findings into teaching materials in the following year to facilitate the discussion when students debriefed their findings.

KEYWORDS

Reading behavior, browsing behavior, information activity, contextual inquiry.

INTRODUCTION

In 2013, the government initiated "bookcrossing movement" to expand bookcrossing stations nationwide at train stations, metro stations, bus stops, and even on certain bus routes in the metropolitan areas around the capital city, where people can borrow a book from the bookcrossing station to read and return a book at any station for other people to read (Department of Health, 2013). While bookcrossing stations at many locations worked fine, those on the bus did not function well and were removed after several months. Observing people's reading on public transit can be a way to understand the reading habits of the general public and may help design and improve programs such as bookcrossing stations and other interventions to promote reading.

Contextual inquiry is an ethnographic approach that typically uses observation and/or in-depth interviews to investigate specific practices by sampling a small group of people in real-world settings (Salazar, 2020). While contextual inquiry has been widely used in user-centered design (e.g., Borghouts et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2014; Jensen et al., 2013), it can help understand people's behavior and thus can be applied to investigating people's information behavior (e.g., Dixon et al., 2022; Feng & Agosto, 2017; Kukka et al., 2018; Maceviciute et al., 2010).

When developing an information behavior course with a unit addressing contextual inquiry, the instructor designed an observation task for students to collaborate on depicting people's reading and browsing behavior on public transit with a set of research questions: Who read on public transit? And how do people read and browse on public transit?

PROCEDURE

In order to introduce how contextual inquiry may be used in information behavior research, the instructor integrated reading and browsing behavior which was introduced in earlier weeks in the course and designed a task for students to conduct unobtrusive observation on public transit. Each student was asked to contribute three cases. During the pandemic when courses went online, students were not asked to contribute a specific number of cases. Instead, they were encouraged to share cases and had the flexibility to use shared cases observed by students in another group for their in-class discussion. The task was assigned four to five weeks before the in-class debrief discussion session. It is feasible for students to complete the observation task because most students commute to school daily. Among 26% of students who live in university housing, those who live in an off-campus dormitory or apartment still need to commute to school. Only students who live on campus do not need to commute to school. However, they typically take public transit for other purposes quite frequently when commuting to work, attending activities, or meeting family and other friends.

Contextual inquiry, including the unobtrusive observation method and in-depth interviews, was introduced in class. The motivations and design used to depict reading and browsing behavior on public transit were also introduced in class before students started their tasks. A shared Google spreadsheet created as a field note template was also introduced and provided to the students to take notes.

Students worked in groups of four to six. After students had done their observation task, each group shared what they observed with peers in their group in class. They were instructed to rebuild their cases by describing the contexts along with the reading and browsing behavior they observed. Following the contextual inquiry procedure, they discussed

and tried to identify wall-worthy notes and highlights based on data. The instructor provided students with a worksheet guiding them with steps of contextual inquiry and breakdowns of the research questions. Preliminary thoughts were generated and debriefed in class. The instructor consolidated students' findings based on their observation notes and integrated the findings into teaching materials in the following year to facilitate the discussion when students debriefed their findings. The instructor also leaves an option for the students to delete their observation notes after grading has finished if they do not want their field notes to be further analyzed as a collective longitudinal dataset.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Over the last ten years, from 2014 to 2023, about 435 students collected a total of 1307 valid cases ranging from 106 to 185 cases per year. Table 1 shows the distribution of cases observed at different types of public transit. Almost all cases were observed on the metro transit system and different bus routes. Among the 1307 cases, about 60% were female and 55% were students. While students mostly study on public transit, other people seem to perform more diverse reading and browsing tasks. The travel time, crowdedness, and stableness on different types of public transit may also affect people's reading and browsing behavior, especially how focused they are, the tasks they perform, the genres/materials read, and the devices used.

Type of Public Transit	Cases	Percentage
Metro	832	63.66%
Bus	309	23.64%
Train	52	3.98%
High-Speed Train	47	3.60%
Coach	38	2.91%
Other	29	2.22%
Total	1307	100%

Table 1. Observed Reading and Browsing Cases on Different Public Transit

Figure 1 shows students' in-class discussions and how they followed the steps to generate their affinity maps and preliminary findings. Students shared the cases they observed with their peers in the group and started to identify wall-worthy categories. Students were encouraged to have several attempts to group their cases in different ways and come up with different hierarchies of their categories to form their affinity maps and discuss their preliminary findings.

Figure 1. Students Developing Affinity Maps in Groups

After students shared their thoughts with the class during the debriefing session, the instructor also made a debrief and shared what has been consolidated in the previous years with the class. The instructor reminded the students to pay close attention to disagreements during the discussion. Some disagreements were raised during the debrief session and the instructor may guide the students to reflect the situation with relevant literature but leave open options for the students. Students were typically able to resolve the disagreements with one another and come up with their final decision on how they would like to depict the phenomenon or how much or how limited they can generalize based on the data they obtained. Bookcrossing policy and intervention implications were discussed if class schedule permits.

FUTURE WORK

This poster shares insights on potential pedagogical design addressing the contextual inquiry approach and provides pedagogical implications for instructors to adopt and adapt the current pedagogic activity design and engage students in collective interpretation. Based on the experience guiding this contextual-inquiry pedagogic activity, providing appropriate training through lectures with clear observation protocol is essential. The current work presents a case integrating collective interpretation activity into a course. This collective dataset may be accumulated and then used in a longitudinal investigation. In the current course design, it is difficult to sample specific metro and bus routes during specific time periods in a systematic way, and the collective interpretation was made within a limited time during the class session each year. With these limitations in mind, future work can further analyze the collective longitudinal data so that potential changes over the years can be revealed and discussed.

REFERENCES

- Borghouts, J., Brumby, D. P., & Cox, A. L. (2020). TimeToFocus: Feedback on Interruption Durations Discourages Distractions and Shortens Interruptions. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human, 27*(5), 1-31. doi:10.1145/3396044
- Department of Health (2013). Bookcrossing movement promotion. Retrieved from <https://www.health.ntpc.gov.tw/en/basic/?mode=detail&node=383>
- Dixon, E., Anderson, J., Blackwelder, D. C., Radnofsky, M. L., & Lazar, A. (2022). The human need for equilibrium: Qualitative study on the ingenuity, technical competency, and changing strategies of people with dementia seeking health information. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. doi:10.2196/35072
- Feng, Y., & Agosto, D. E. (2017). The experience of mobile information overload: Struggling between needs and constraints. *Information Research, 22*(2), paper 754. Retrieved from <http://InformationR.net/ir/22-2/paper754.html>
- Huang, K. L., Chen, K. H., & Ho, C. H. (2014). Enhancement of reading experience: Users' behavior patterns and the interactive interface design of tablet readers. *Library Hi Tech, 32*(3), 509-528.
- Jensen, A. E., Jægerfelt, C. M., Francis, S., Larsen, B., & Bogers, T. (2018). I just scroll through my stuff until I find it or give up: A contextual inquiry of PIM on private handheld devices. In *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference on Human Information Interaction & Retrieval* (pp. 140-149).
- Kukka, H., Kostakos, V., Ojala, T., Ylipulli, J., Suopajaärvi, T., Jurmu, M., & Hosio, S. (2013). This is not classified: everyday information seeking and encountering in smart urban spaces. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing, 17*, 15–27. doi:10.1007/s00779-011-0474-1
- Lawrence, K., & Costello, D. (2014, April 16th). Contextual inquiry: A must-have method for your user research toolbox. ASIS&T SIG USE Webinar. Retrieved from <https://www.asist.org/meetings-events/webinars/contextual-inquiry-a-must-have-method-for-your-user-research-toolbox/>
- Maceviciute, E., & Wilson, T. D. (2010). Information behaviour research and information systems development: the SHAMAN project, an example of collaboration. *Information Research, 15*(4), paper 445. <http://InformationR.net/ir/15-4/paper445.html>
- Salazar, K. (2020). Contextual Inquiry: Inspire Design by Observing and Interviewing Users in Their Context. Retrieved from <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/contextual-inquiry/>